

Angelo Leogrando^{1*o^}
*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU
°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU
^University of Bari Aldo Moro

Public-Private Scientific Co-Publications Across Italian Regions

Public-private scientific co-publications grew by an average of 29.24% in Italian regions between 2018 and 2023.

Eurostat calculates public-private publications. The indicator consists of a ratio. The numerator is the number of research publications with public-private co-authors. The definition of "private sector" excludes the private medical-health sector. Publications are assigned to the country where the private sector enterprises or other organizations are based. The denominator is the total population. The indicator captures public-private research links and active collaboration activities between researchers from the business sector and public sector researchers that have resulted in academic publications.

Public-Private Scientific Co-Publications in 2023. Based on the data, Trentino Alto Adige stands out significantly with 256.11 publications, suggesting a strong collaborative network between academic institutions and industry within this region. Given its strong tradition in research, especially in engineering, agriculture, and information technology sectors, it is plausible that Trentino Alto Adige enjoys a favorable environment for joint research between universities and the private sector. This could reflect a high capacity to attract funding for joint projects and a high level of integration between academic research and industrial applications. Liguria and Molise also show high numbers, with 210.21 and 210.06 respectively. These figures may indicate a well-established presence of research infrastructure and regional policies focused on supporting collaboration between universities and industry. On the other hand, regions like Calabria and Basilicata, with 124.98 and 140.37 respectively, seem to have less co-publication activity. This can be attributed to various factors, including a lower concentration of universities with a strong research orientation or less collaboration with the private sector. However, even these lower numbers can represent significant opportunities for these regions to develop more aggressive policies to increase collaboration between the public and private sectors. The Lazio region shows a significant number of co-publications (188.24), which is expected given the presence of numerous universities and research institutions, as well as a variety of high-tech industries. This suggests a well-established synergy between academic research and industrial development, possibly facilitated by government policy and specific regional incentives.

¹Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrando.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

Emilia Romagna and Tuscany, with 189.39 and 198.56 publications respectively, are known for their dynamic economies and strong support for research and development. The analysis of public-private scientific co-publications in Italy shows a varied landscape, with some regions standing out for intense collaborative activity.

Public-Private Scientific Co-Publications between 2018 and 2023. The data highlight not only the absolute increase in the number of publications during this period but also the percentage growth, which varies significantly from region to region. The region with the most marked growth, Valle d'Aosta, saw an impressive increase of 75.66% in co-publications, rising from 87.40 in 2018 to 153.53 in 2023. This figure may reflect a renewed focus on research and development or the establishment of new policies to incentivize collaboration between universities and the private sector. It is noteworthy that such an increase occurred in one of the smallest regions, suggesting that limited size can be compensated by effective policies and strategic collaborations. Molise showed the second highest percentage growth with 71.59%, implying a significant expansion of research activities. This growth from 122.42 to 210.06 can be justified by increased investments in research and a rise in collaboration between the local university and businesses. Conversely, regions with the lowest growth rates, such as Lazio and Lombardy, show increases of 15.13% and 15.87% respectively. Despite these more modest figures, the total volume of publications remains high, indicating an already well-developed research base that continues to grow at a slower pace. Regions traditionally recognized as innovation hubs, such as Emilia Romagna and Tuscany, saw growths of 23.49% and 12.83% respectively. This suggests a continued, albeit more gradual, expansion of their research capacities, consolidating their position as leaders in scientific and technological innovation. An interesting case is represented by Trentino Alto Adige, which not only recorded one of the highest absolute increases (+47.75) but also an important percentage growth (+22.92%). This reflects the effectiveness of regional policies aimed at incentivizing collaborative research and indicates a highly synergistic environment between universities and businesses. Regional variations can be attributed to several factors, including regional policies, the presence of universities and research centers, industrial specializations, and the effectiveness of public-private collaborations. The impact of these collaborations is not only quantitative but also qualitative, directly influencing the type of research conducted and its practical application in local industries. The analysis of data between 2018 and 2023 reveals a varied landscape of growth and development in the field of scientific co-publications in Italy. This phenomenon not only highlights regions that are emerging as new research and innovation centers but also underscores the importance of policies supporting scientific collaboration as a lever for regional technological and economic development. Significant differences in percentage growth further emphasize the need for tailored strategies for each region, capable of maximizing local potentials and promoting balanced and sustainable growth.

Italian Macro-Regions between 2018 and 2023. The analysis of public-private scientific co-publications in Italy, broken down by macro-geographical areas – South, North, and Center – between 2018 and 2023, reveals significant absolute and percentage variations that deserve in-depth examination. These data not only illustrate the dynamics of collaboration between the public and private sectors in the academic and industrial fields but also provide an overview of the evolution of research and innovation in different parts of the country. In 2018, the South recorded 112.56 co-publications, a number that increased to 158.54 in 2023, showing an absolute increase of 45.98 units and a notable percentage increase of 40.85%. This marked development can be interpreted as the

result of policies focused on promoting research and technological development in these regions, traditionally less involved in innovation circuits compared to the North. The increase reflects a growing integration between universities and local industries, often stimulated by specific funding and regional initiatives aimed at bridging the technological and scientific gap with other areas of the country. The North, which has historically boasted a robust ecosystem of research and industrial collaboration, also shows an increase, rising from 150.61 co-publications in 2018 to 189.93 in 2023. The absolute increase of 39.31 units and the percentage growth of 26.10% indicate a continuous expansion of collaborative research activities, albeit at a slower pace compared to the South. This could be due to the saturation of some research areas or the greater maturity of the innovation ecosystem, which already sees a dense network of existing collaborations. As for the Center, the increase has been more moderate, with a rise from 149.15 co-publications in 2018 to 176.08 in 2023. This corresponds to an absolute increase of 26.94 and a percentage growth of 18.06%. Here too, the growth can be attributed to the expansion of synergies between universities and industries, although at a less intense pace compared to the South. It may reflect a phase of consolidation rather than rapid expansion, with an increasing emphasis on the quality and impact of collaborative research. These regional variations in the number of co-publications reflect different regional realities and dynamics in Italy. The South, with its marked increase, could be seen as a positive signal of a shift towards greater equity in the distribution of research and innovation activities. On the other hand, the North continues to build on an existing solid base, while the Center moves at a more measured pace, potentially focusing its resources on higher-profile initiatives or specific areas of specialization. In summary, the data between 2018 and 2023 illustrate not only a general expansion of public-private scientific co-publications in Italy but also an evolution of regional dynamics that could influence future research and development policies.

North-South Divide. The data on public-private scientific co-publications between 2018 and 2023 show an evident divide between Northern and Southern Italy, but also reveal a positive trend suggesting a potential reduction of this discrepancy. Initially, the North had a significant advantage, with a higher number of co-publications compared to the South. However, during the period considered, the South recorded a percentage increase of 40.85%, higher than the 26.10% of the North, indicating accelerated growth. This increase is also reflected in the absolute growth, where the South saw an increase of 45.98 units compared to the 39.31 units of the North, despite starting from a lower base. These changes result from targeted policies aimed at stimulating research and innovation in the southern regions through investments in research infrastructure, incentives for collaborations between universities and industries, and an improvement in higher education offerings. Such efforts are essential to compensate for historical disparities, which have seen the North more favored in terms of economic and industrial development, and a higher density of industrial and academic fabric.

Conclusions. The value of public-private co-publications grew by an average of 29.24% in Italian regions between 2018 and 2023. Looking at the macro-regions, we can see an average growth of 18.06% between 2018 and 2023. However, the macro-region where this variable grew the most is Southern Italy with +40.85%, followed by the North at +26.10%, and the Center with +18.06%. In absolute terms, the North has a higher level of public-private scientific co-publications than both the Center and the South. The higher levels of this variable in Northern Italy are due to three factors: the high number of research centers and universities, the high number of companies willing to collaborate with public entities, and a general climate oriented towards public-private co-participation. A cultural climate that needs to be promoted also in Central and Southern Italy.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

References

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A.(2020). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(11), 166-187.

Leogrande, A., Saponaro, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). A GIS based estimation of quality of life in Italian regions. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)* e-ISSN.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The intellectual assets in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3956755*.

Magazzino, C., & Leogrande, A. (2020). Subjective well-being in Italian regions: A panel data approach.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The attractiveness of European research systems. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(10), 72-101.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Research and Development Expenditures on ESG Model in the Global Economy. *Available at SSRN 4414232*.

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Rule of Law in the ESG Framework in the World Economy. *Available at SSRN 4355016*.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The impact of R&D investments on corporate performance in European Countries. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(7), 186-201.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4406997*.

Leogrande, A., Laureti, L., & Costantiello, A. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4091597*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4021150*.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Labor Force Participation Rate in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4466452*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. *Available at SSRN 4398483*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. *Available at SSRN 4324938*.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3983218*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Satisfaction with the Environmental Condition in the Italian Regions between 2004 and 2020. *Available at SSRN 4061708*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Foreign Doctorate Students in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4032975*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment in Innovative Enterprises in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4010098*.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Landscape and Cultural Heritage Among Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2019. *Available at SSRN 3971174*.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The Determinants of Innovation in European Countries in the period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(8), 91-126.

Ferri, G., & Leogrande, A. (2015). Was the Crisis due to a shift from stakeholder to shareholder finance? Surveying the debate.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Massaro, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Role of Renewable Energy Consumption in Promoting Sustainability and Circular Economy: A Data-Driven Analysis. In *Data-Driven Intelligent Business Sustainability* (pp. 360-386). IGI Global.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Role of GDP Growth in the ESG Approach at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4434206*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Regulatory Quality and ESG Model at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4388957*.

Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., & Massaro, A. (2022). Fixed Broadband Take-Up in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4034298*.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Design Applications in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3956853*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). THE DETERMINANTS OF FIRM INVESTMENTS IN RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT. In *IAI ACADEMIC CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS Education and Social Sciences Business and Economics* (pp. 55-67).

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The regulatory quality in the light of environmental, social and governance framework at world level. *Discover Global Society*, 2(1), 1-20.

Magazzino, C., Madaleno, M., Waqas, M., & Leogrande, A. (2024). Exploring the determinants of methane emissions from a worldwide perspective using panel data and machine learning analyses. *Environmental Pollution*, 348, 123807.

Appendix

Public-Private Scientific Co-Publications in Italian Regions: 2018 vs 2023

Public-Private Co-Publications by Macro Regions: 2018 vs 2023

Public-Private Scientific Co-Publications in Italian Regions (2023)

